

EFFECT OF THERMAL MODIFICATION ON THE FIRE PERFORMANCE OF STRAND-BASED MASS TIMBER COMPOSITE PANELS

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ABSTRACT

The demand for mass timber panels has risen sharply, driven by the growing need for sustainable construction materials. However, concerns regarding the durability and fire performance of wood-based composite materials have led to the development of various treatment processes. Among them, thermal modification is a widely adopted process in the industry to enhance the dimensional stability and durability of wood-based materials. At the same time, the emphasis on high-quality lumber for cross-laminated timber (CLT) panels has diminished the utilization of small-diameter timber (SDT) for CLT panels. Effective use of SDT is essential for maintaining forest health and mitigating forest fires. This study explores the use of SDT strands, both untreated and thermally modified, in the production of mass timber panels. Thermal treatment was conducted in an industrial autoclave to ensure uniform processing. The resulting composite panels exhibited excellent mechanical performance, notably enhanced shear strength due to the reduction of rolling shear effects. Fire testing revealed that thermal modification had no significant impact on either fire reaction or fire resistance properties of the mass timber panels produced using control and thermally modified wood strand composite material. While the flexural stiffness remained largely unchanged, the panels demonstrated slight reductions in flexural strength and significant improvements in shear and internal bond strength.

1 INTRODUCTION

Sustainable materials have seen an increase in interest for different applications in the built environment [1]. The use of cross-laminated timber (CLT), which can transfer forces in two directions, has been one such application in demand as a sustainable building construction material [2].

Traditionally, these CLT panels are made from high-quality lumber, the processing of which is economically viable to the sawmills [2]. The manufacturing cost of CLTs is higher than that of other wood-based panels due to the stringent quality control protocols for the lumber that is used in the panels. However, low-quality small-diameter logs are readily available in the US forests as a result of hazardous fuel-removal thinning operations to mitigate forest fires and ensure healthy forests [3-5]. There is commercial interest in producing value-added products using these small-diameter logs, and manufacturing mass timber panels using strand-based technology fits the bill as it does not require high-quality lumber for the production of wood strand composite materials [3, 6-8].

One of the primary challenges in using cross-laminated timber (CLT) for exterior applications is its high susceptibility to moisture uptake [9], which significantly limits its use in outdoor environments. To address this limitation, various strategies have been explored, most notably, chemical modification of the wood to enhance its dimensional stability and overall durability. However, chemical modifications, such as chromated copper arsenical and micronized copper azole, are known to be hazardous to the environment. Enhancing the usability of SDT necessitates procedures that improve its longevity, dimensional stability, and overall product performance while imparting minimal damage to the environment. This study proposes the method of thermal modification of strands to achieve more dimensionally stable and more durable mass timber panels [1]. Thermal modification has been studied extensively for lumber to enhance its dimensional stability and durability. Thermal modification (TM) provides a sustainable substitute for chemical alteration, using heat as the principal agent in either dry or wet conditions. In wet processes, water or steam is used, with the possibility of recycling waste for energy recovery or biofuel generation. Dry techniques use air or inert atmospheres for comparable advantages [10]. TM reduces wood's hydrophilicity by partially extracting hemicellulosic sugars [11], thus improving dimensional stability and decay resistance. Pressurized settings further expedite the breakdown of the complex hemicellulose structure, thus imparting decay resistance and decreasing moisture absorption while preserving or marginally increasing stiffness as the degree of crystallinity is increased [12]. Therefore, the current research employed a pressurized TM technique for the strands to augment hemicellulose breakdown, strengthen resistance to fungal decay, and alleviate moisture-related problems while preserving mechanical integrity.

Fire performance is a critical consideration for mass timber panels, especially in light of increasingly stringent global fire safety regulations for building materials. While wood offers several advantages as a structural material, its inherent combustibility poses challenges in applications requiring enhanced fire resistance [13]. One potential mitigation strategy involves the use of organic wood preservatives—traditionally applied to protect against biological degradation, which may also influence the material's combustion behavior [14]. Investigations examining the combustion characteristics of prevalent species such as Norway spruce (*Picea abies*) and Scots pine (*Pinus sylvestris*) have shown distinct species-specific variations in burn patterns, mass loss, and charring zone thickness [15]. Similar variations are found in heat-treated woods. The findings are affected by wood density, resin content, and preservative treatments [15]. Comprehensive studies on the influence of TM on the fire performance of full-scale structures are limited. Additionally, there is also a divided belief on the advantages or disadvantages of TM on the fire performance of mass timber panels [8, 9]. Thus, it is also critical to have a comprehensive understanding of the influence of TM on strand-based mass timber panels, in both fire reaction and fire resistance properties. Therefore, the objectives of this study are to evaluate the effects of thermal modification on the structural performance of the proposed strand-based wood composite mass timber panels and to investigate the influence of thermal modification on the fire reaction and fire resistance properties of the panels.

2 MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Panel production

Wood strands were produced from lower-grade lumber sourced from small-diameter Engelmann spruce (*Picea engelmannii*) and lodgepole pine (*Pinus contorta*), referred to as ESLP. The materials were procured from Idaho Forest Group. The sourced timber (thickness between 25.4 to 50.8 mm) was cut into 150 mm long slats, soaked in water to increase the moisture content above the fiber saturation point to around 40-50%, and stranded using a CAE disc strander (Kadant, Inc.) at WSU's Composite

Materials and Engineering Center (CMEC). The generated wood strands were approximately 148 mm in length, 19 mm to 38 mm in width, and 0.381 mm to 0.508 mm in thickness. The produced stands were then conditioned at 21.1°C and 65% relative humidity (RH) to attain a moisture content of 12% before thermal modification. The TM was carried out in an industrial autoclave at Therma Wood Technologies (TWT), Ronan, Montana, USA. The modification was carried out in an inert condition, using nitrogen, at 165°C and 0.8 MPa pressure in a 12 m³ autoclave for 7.5 h.

After thermal treatment, the strands were again conditioned at 21.1°C and 65% RH for about three weeks before making flat 6.35 mm thick, 1220 mm wide, and 2440 mm long veneers with a target density of 640 kg/m³. Polymeric methyl diphenyl diisocyanate (pMDI) adhesive, supplied by Henkel, was applied at 5 wt.% and atomized onto the strands using a drum blender. The veneers were made with strands oriented primarily along the long direction in a hot press (Ironworks Press Machine). The veneers were then assembled into laminated strand veneer lumber (LSVL) with final dimensions of 38.1 mm in thickness, 610 mm in width, and 2440 mm in length. The sanded veneers were initially coated using a 10 wt% aqueous solution of primer (Loctite HB 3105) before applying the polyurethane (PUR) adhesive (HBX 602 PURBOND). PUR was applied at a coverage rate of 20 g/m², using the automated glue spreading technique of the USNR CLT Press 1.83 m by 3.66 m (USNR, Woodland, Washington, USA), available at WSU's CMEC. The same press from Ironworks was then used to make the LSVL panels, details of which are provided in [1]. The LSVL panels were then cross-laminated to develop the cross-laminated strand veneer lumber (CLSVL), using the same PUR adhesive with a 20 g/m² spread rate. Cold pressing was used for making both LSVL and CLSVL panels. The final CLSVL panels were made at a thickness of 114.3 mm, a length of 3000 mm, and a width of 1830 mm. The USNR CLT Press was utilized to make the CLSVL panels.

2.2 Mechanical performance

Flatwise third-point bending tests were performed according to ASTM D198-22a [18], where a span-to-depth ratio of 18 was maintained for the CLSVL (2286 mm by 305 mm by 114 mm) panels. A 222 kN load cell, attached to a hydraulic actuator, with string pots having stroke lengths of 250 mm, available at WSU's CMEC, was used for performing the flexural tests. The test setup is provided in Figure 1 (a). Flatwise center-point bending tests were again conducted to ascertain the shear characteristics of the mass timber panels, again as per ASTM D198-22a standard [18]. Here, the span-to-depth ratios for both the panel types were reduced to four, as per the standard, resulting in 203 mm long, 89 mm wide, and 38 mm thick LSVL panels and 584 mm long, 305 mm wide, and 114 mm thick CLSVL panels. The same 222 kN load cell and strain pots were used. The testing setup is illustrated in Figure 1 (b).

Figure 1: Illustration of the testing setups for (a) flexural test and (b) shear test as per ASTM D198-22a standard [18].

2.3 Fire performance

Bench-scale cone calorimeter tests were also conducted as per the ASTM E1354-23 [19]. The tests were carried out in the horizontal orientation at the University of Auckland (UoA), New Zealand, on the CLSVL panels prepared from both thermally treated strands and untreated (control) strands. The

limitation in sample holder thickness at UoA (50 mm) required the CLSVL samples to be cut in half to ensure the thickness of each specimen was less than 50 mm. The sample dimensions were maintained at 100 mm by 100 mm. The ASTM E119-24 [20] standard was followed to perform the fire resistance testing at two different scales on the CLSVL panels at Western Fire Center. A small-scale furnace test was eventually carried out with 1.19 m by 1.5 m by 0.11 m samples, which were not loaded and the fire rating was calculated based on either the time the wall resisted the heat transmission in a way that the unexposed side did not reach a temperature of 139°C or the time when the panel failed structurally due to buckling at the junctions under gravity load. Sixteen thermocouples were installed on each panel to monitor temperatures at every 38.1 mm increment through the panel thickness, extending up to 114.3 mm from the exposed surface to also monitor the temperature on the unexposed side. The full-scale furnace tests on horizontal walls were then carried out with 3.01 m by 3.5 m by 0.11 m samples, as per the ASTM E119-24 standard. The standard requires a minimum 9.3 m² surface area of exposure, which was met in the current study. The samples were loaded in compression with a uniformly distributed load of 355.86 kN, which resulted in 9.43 kN/m of loading as per the anticipated loading of 2-layered structures. The fire rating was again calculated based on either the time the wall with the compression loads resisted the heat transmission until the temperature on the unexposed side reached 139°C or the time when the wall panels failed under the gravity and applied loads. Twenty thermocouples were used in each panel, six equally distributed at 38.1 mm depths until the unexposed side was reached, with two at the junctions on the unexposed side created during the assembly of the LSVL panels.

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Mechanical testing revealed significant advantages of the strand-based mass timber panels, termed cross-laminated strand veneer lumber (CLSVL), over conventional CLT panels; particularly the elimination of rolling shear, a common failure mode that limits the load-carrying capacity of CLT in high-rise constructions. Additionally, CLSVL demonstrated comparable or superior mechanical performance in several aspects when compared to other mass timber panels made from the same species [21]. Figures 2 (a) and (b) illustrate the comparative effective bending and shear stiffnesses, respectively, of the mass timber panels. The elimination of rolling shear failure [6] resulted in a significant increase in the shear stiffness of the strand-based panels, resulting due to the distribution in grain orientation in the plane of the panel. Internal bond strengths of the composites, as per ASTM D1037-13 [22], also showed enhanced performance with values of 1.08 MPa (COV = 16 %) compared to only 0.3 MPa (COV = 46 %) for the panels made from control or not thermally modified strands.

Figure 2: Comparative test results for (a) effective bending stiffness and (b) effective shear stiffness.

Fire reaction property analysis using a bench-scale cone calorimeter, as per ASTM E1354-23, showed similar trends in heat release rate (HRR) and mass loss for both CLSVL panels made from control (C-CLSVL) and thermally modified (T-CLSVL) strands, as illustrated in Figure 2. The peak

heat release rate (PHRR) shifted, with higher values for the T-CLSVL ($351.7 \pm 41.1 \text{ kW/m}^2$), compared to $310.1 \pm 10.1 \text{ kW/m}^2$ for the control samples, Figure 3 (a). Although the time to PHRR was longer for the T-CLSVL panels ($45 \pm 5.4 \text{ sec}$) compared to $35 \pm 6.2 \text{ sec}$ for the control. The total heat evolved was also almost similar for both the panel types tested. The time to ignition was longer for the T-CLSVL panels by about 33% compared to the C-CLSVL panels, which can be attributed to the reduced amount of weak hemicellulose and volatiles from the surface. The time to flameout was almost similar with only 6% average variation. This indicates that although the time to ignition was later, the amount of fuel in the material reduced during the TM process, resulting in a similar time of flameout. Both samples showed good barriers against flame propagation, with an initial peak in HRR and then a steady, low HRR throughout the burning phase, as can be observed from Figure 3 (a). These are synchronous to fire-resistant specimens, showing a significant amount of char formation on the upper layers that can protect the subsequent layers, giving a good amount of time for evacuating the premises during fire. The mass loss rate was similar for both samples, as can be observed from Figure 3 (b). The char formed in the T-CLSVL samples was 3.3% of the initial mass, 40% higher than that of the control specimen. The T-CLSVL samples also took 33% longer to ignite and 22% longer to reach the PHRR, indicating better fire reaction properties compared to the control. However, the time to flameout was lower by 6%, which again can be attributed to the lower availability of fuel due to the loss in TM. The total heat evolved was almost similar, with the T-CLSVL having a slightly higher PHRR by about 11.8%. Overall, both the C-CLSVL and the T-CLSVL showed promising fire reaction properties.

Figure 3: Representation of the (a) HRR and (b) mass loss percentage of the control and TM CLSVL panels when tested in the cone-calorimeter as per the ASTM E1354-23 standard

Small-scale fire resistance tests on C-CLSVL and T-CLSVL panels, based on ASTM E119-22 standard, were performed. Control and TM strands were used to fabricate 24 veneers that were 1.22 m by 1.83 m (4 ft by 6 ft) for the layup of the panels. The control veneers had an average density of $642.34 \pm 40 \text{ kg/m}^3$ ($40.1 \pm 2.5 \text{ lb/ft}^3$), and the TM veneers had $644.58 \pm 16.02 \text{ kg/m}^3$ ($40.24 \pm 1 \text{ lb/ft}^3$). The final wall assembly, after installation, was 1.19 m by 1.5 m by 0.11 m. These specimens were not loaded, therefore, the main criterion for judgment, as per ASTM E119-20, was that the transmission of heat through the wall will not have raised the temperature on its unexposed side more than 139°C (average) above its initial temperature, or if a temperature higher than 30% (181°C) of the specified limit occurs

at any one point (single-point) on the unexposed side of the assembly. Both specimens were able to meet the 1-hr wall rating requirement, with the control being able to maintain the testing criteria for 102 min (rounded off to the nearest integral minute). The treated had a successful test for 64 min (corrected time), after which, although the sample did not fail, the testing apparatus failed to maintain pressure. A comparison of the temperatures on the three levels of the panels (1.5 in or 38.1 mm layer, 3 in or 76.2 mm layer, and unexposed side) at 60 mins showed that the C-CLSVL samples had better fire resistance compared to the TM counterparts.

Finally, full-scale vertical fire resistance testing, as per ASTM E119-20, was carried out on the panels with a continuous compressive load on the top surface, as illustrated in Figure 4. The load-bearing calculations were carried out as per the expected loading on 2-layered structures, which came out to be 9.43 kN/m or 6957 lb/ft, giving a total load of 355.86 kN or 80,000 lbs. The utilization ratio of 0.163, as per interaction equations, was used to understand the loading requirements. The results further strengthened the previous conclusion from the small-scale test, that both wall structures successfully met the 1-hr load requirements. However, similar to small-scale testing, the C-CLSVL panel was able to withstand the load for 71 mins, compared to 64 mins by the T-CLSVL wall specimen. The control performed slightly better under fire resistance, which might be attributed to the reduction in strength due to the TM of the strands. It must also be noted that the panels failed due to buckling under compression loads at the joints in the outer layer, as illustrated in Figure 3. Thus, if the veneers were laminated directly without processing them into lumber, the buckling issue could be eliminated. This has the potential to enhance the fire rating of the panels and possibly impart better fire resistance properties of the T-CLSVL panels due to the enhanced stiffnesses.

Figure 3: Loaded full-scale wall test for (a) C-CLSVL and (b) T-CLSVL before and after fire test as per ASTM E119-20 vertical wall testing procedure.

4 CONCLUSIONS

Thermal modification had an overall positive impact on the mechanical properties of the panels, evidenced by a 260% increase in internal bond strength and a 21% improvement in both effective bending and shear stiffnesses, without a statistically significant change in flexural strength. In contrast, its effect on fire performance was largely neutral, with no significant differences in most fire reaction and resistance metrics; however, a slight decline in the overall fire rating was observed. To address this limitation and meet fire safety standards, the application of an external fire-resistant layer—such as gypsum board, which is commonly used in buildings worldwide—is proposed. Given the environmental concerns and non-renewable nature of gypsum, alternative solutions are being explored. Preliminary research is investigating the use of fire-resistant fabrics, which may enhance fire performance while reducing reliance on gypsum-based materials in residential construction. Additionally, the lab-scale requirement of sectioning the LSVL panels for sanding and priming, if eliminated, can potentially reduce the buckling issues at the joints and possibly increase the fire rating of the overall panels, where the enhanced stiffness due to thermal modification can potentially also help increase the fire resistance properties of the panels.

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